

BRIEFING PAPER

Isca Evidence, University of Exeter: April 2026

The effectiveness of contact tracing to reduce transmission of infectious disease as part of epidemic or pandemic response: a rapid systematic review

Public Health and Social Measures (PHSM) are actions taken by individuals, communities and governments to reduce the spread of infection during epidemics and pandemics, particularly before vaccines or treatments are widely available.¹ Contact tracing (CT) is one such measure. When someone is infected, the people they have been in close contact with are at risk of becoming infected and passing the infection on. CT involves identifying and reaching these contacts and supporting them to access testing, treatment or advice on self-isolation, where appropriate.² Although CT has been widely used, there remains uncertainty about how effective different CT approaches are in reducing transmission, and what unintended consequences they may have.

The UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) has a remit to protect every member of every community from the impact of infectious diseases.³ We were therefore commissioned by the UKHSA to undertake a rapid systematic review to evaluate the effectiveness of CT for different pathogens and transmission routes, in the context of epidemic or pandemic response.

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This is a high-level overview of our research to inform decision-making. Further outputs including plain language summaries and academic papers are available:

Key Findings

- Evidence was clustered under two broad routes of transmission:
 - Airborne: Tuberculosis (TB) and COVID-19 were the only two infections covered.
 - Bloodborne/Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs): HIV and bacterial/parasitic STIs formed the largest set.
- Most studies reported that infection/disease control was neither improved nor worsened with CT. There was some evidence of reduced disease prevalence and incidence for tuberculosis CT.
- More than half of the studies were considered of weak quality.
- Some evidence suggested that healthcare provider-led CT methods may be more effective than patient-led methods in STI contexts, but conclusions remain limited by heterogeneity and weak study quality overall.
- Unintended consequences were very rarely assessed (only two studies), limiting confident conclusions.
- Equity was considered only in a minority of studies; evidence was too diffuse to make clear assessments.

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Context

Public Health and Social Measures (PHSM) are a key line of defence in health emergencies, particularly before vaccines and treatments are available at scale.¹

Contact Tracing is a core public health tool used to control the spread of infections, yet its effectiveness across different diseases and contexts is not well established.⁴

Evidence that can be generalised across infectious diseases is limited, highlighting the need for an up-to-date synthesis focused on the core process of reaching contacts.

Why and how did we do this review?

Review rationale – the ‘why’

The UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) is responsible for protecting communities from infectious disease threats and ensuring the UK is prepared to respond to health emergencies.³

To support this, governments and health authorities rely on CT as part of emergency epidemic/pandemic response, yet decision-making is complicated by uncertainty about:

- how effective different CT methods are at reducing transmission across different infections and settings, and
- how CT may lead to unintended effects and what these unintended consequences might be.

Previous reviews have often focused on a single disease, included modelling studies rather than real-world evidence, or examined CT strategies that are not easily transferable across different infections. Some are also now out of date.

To address the broad remit of the UKHSA, we undertook this comprehensive, up-to-date synthesis focused on aspects of CT that could be generalisable across a range of conditions. This review will inform the development of UKHSA advice and guidance as part of pandemic preparedness and to help inform research priorities and future evaluation and improvement approaches to contact tracing.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement

This review was strengthened by the involvement of a group of around 17 public collaborators, called PERSPEX. This culturally, geographically and demographically diverse group meet monthly, and bring carer, patient, or public perspectives to Isca Evidence: <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/research/groups/medicine/esmi/workstreams/perspex/>.

Over the course of this review, we discussed the review three times with PERSPEX, between December 2024 and March 2025. We introduced the concept of CT and discussed its use in public health. We also listened to their experiences, concerns, and perspectives relating to the main findings of our review, and CT in general.

Overall, these discussions helped provide a public perspective on CT acceptability, potential harms, and the importance of unintended consequences and equity considerations in how CT is evaluated and reported.

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How did we find the evidence

After removing duplicates, non-English language references, 12,816 titles and abstracts were screened for relevance against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. 198 records were included for full-text review and five more were found through supplementary searching. For this rapid review, we included 88 reports of 86 studies evaluating CT. Fifty-five studies were prioritised for full extraction and appraisal as they provided more robust evidence, using comparative designs that allowed CT approaches to be assessed more reliably. None of the 31 deprioritised studies looked at a route of transmission that was not already covered in the prioritised studies.

All extracted data were presented in tables and described. We could not perform any statistical analyses across the different studies because of the variation in designs, interventions and outcomes. Included studies were grouped based on route of transmission and condition/infection. To allow meaningful comparison across studies, the methods of CT were grouped based on whether they were led by a healthcare provider, were patient-led, whether they involved visiting households, and whether they were technology based.

What did we find?

Study characteristics

We included 88 reports of 86 studies evaluating CT, with 55 studies prioritised for full extraction and appraisal due to study design strength.

The evidence came from only two transmission routes. 20 studies focused on airborne infections (tuberculosis, Covid-19) and 35 on bloodborne/sexually transmitted infections (STIs, including HIV).

About 20% of studies considered some form of equity-related factors, but evidence was too diffuse to draw meaningful conclusions.

Most studies examined healthcare provider-led CT, where health professionals or public health teams identified and contacted people exposed to an infected individual.

36 studies were randomised controlled trials (RCTs), including cluster and stepped-wedge RCTs, while 19 studies used non-randomised designs.

Evidence was highly variable (designs, settings, outcomes). More than half of the studies were considered of weak quality. (9 studies were rated 'Strong', 18 'Moderate', and 28 'Weak' overall.)

Unintended consequences (e.g. homelessness, unemployment, partner violence) were rarely measured. Only two studies, both of which were in a sexual health setting, examined unintended effects. These findings may not apply to other diseases or contexts.

Overview of findings

- Overall, the evidence presents a mixed and uncertain picture. No single CT approach consistently showed clear benefits across all diseases, settings or outcomes. More than half of the included studies were rated as methodologically weak, further reducing certainty.
- The evidence base is currently not evenly distributed across routes of transmission. There was no evidence found on food/waterborne, vector-borne (spread by insects or animals), or direct contact infections within the included criteria.
- Studies focusing on TB provided some indications that CT may reduce disease incidence/prevalence. Evidence from STIs suggested that provider-initiated CT may perform better than approaches that rely on patients to notify contacts themselves.
- Rather than comparing CT with no CT, many studies compared one form of CT with another or with "usual care", which was often poorly described. This limits the extent to which firm conclusions can be drawn about overall effectiveness.
- The available evidence offers limited insight into how contact tracing affects different population groups or how equity should inform future implementation.
- Only two studies looked at the unintended effects of CT, both of which examined CT methods in a sexual health context and were focused on intimate partner violence or relationship breakdown.

What are the implications of this review?

Due to the variability of the interventions and outcomes, and poor description of the intervention contexts and comparators, we could not draw any clear conclusions about what worked or what didn't, and why.

The review highlights challenges in generalisability across diseases and health systems. Much of the evidence on STIs focused on partner notifications, where contacts are clearly defined. These approaches may be less transferable to diseases with diffuse or poorly defined contacts, such as those spread by airborne transmission.

Finally, we found limited evidence on unintended effects, despite these being important considerations for trust and acceptability in large-scale responses. Policymakers should consider both intended and unintended effects when planning and scaling CT interventions.

Limitations and strengths

- Many studies compared CT with "usual care", but this was often poorly described, making it difficult to fully assess effectiveness.
- Decisions about study prioritisation were shaped by the rapid and policy-focused nature of the review. While these decisions were transparently documented, it is possible that alternative approaches could have led to different emphases or conclusions. 😞
- Wide-ranging and thorough search strategy, with studies selected and assessed using robust and well-established methods.
- Studies that compared CT approaches against a clear comparison group were prioritised, which helped focus the analysis on more robust evidence. 😊
- Focus on disease control, such as changes in infection rates or treatment outcomes, rather than counts of contacts alone, making the findings more relevant for policy decisions.

Future research

Future studies should test how CT methods work across different diseases, routes of transmission, settings, and geographical areas. Lessons from existing CT programmes can be adapted more deliberately. For example:

- Work from STIs and HIV can inform how to manage stigma, support people into treatment, and use contact-delivered testing where appropriate.
- Evidence from TB can help improve support for household contacts, particularly those at higher risk.
- Experience from COVID-19 can inform how to scale up contact tracing quickly during a pandemic and manage situations where contacts are difficult to clearly define.

Future research should clearly examine whether CT reduces or worsens health inequalities. Studies should more routinely assess unintended effects of contact tracing, including potential harms as well as benefits, building these considerations into evaluation from the outset.

References

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